

Effect of School Environment on the Emotional Maturity of Adolescents Studying in Durg District

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Abstract

The present study examines the impact of the school environment on the emotional Maturity of Adolescents Studying in Durg District. Utilizing a sample of 792 students from government and private schools selected stratified random sampling techniques, the research investigates key variables such as type of school, gender, school environment in relation to their emotional maturity. According to Hurlock, "Emotional maturity involves the kind of living that most richly and fully expresses what a person has in him at a level of his development," is assessed using the Emotional Maturity Scale (by Tara Sabapathy, 2017), while the school environment is evaluated using the School Environment Inventory (Mishra, 2000). The findings reveal that emotional maturity varies according to school type. Gender differences are noted, with female students exhibiting slightly higher emotional maturity scores than males. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) analysis underscore significant impact of the school environment in shaping emotional maturity. The study underscores the critical role of a supportive school environment in fostering emotional maturity, with implications for curriculum design and policy-making. By identifying key environmental factors, this research contributes to a deeper understanding of how schools can empower students to develop emotional resilience and maturity, ultimately preparing them for success in personal and social spheres.

Keywords: Adolescence, School Environment, Emotional Intelligence, Gender

I. Introduction

Education is a vital instrument for empowering people and equipping them to handle life's obstacles. Often called the "passage to progression," it encourages a long-lasting shift in people's thinking that makes it possible for them to distinguish between right and wrong. Fostering knowledge and values is the real purpose of education.

The primary objective of education in schools should be to create individuals capable of doing new things, rather than merely repeating the achievements of past generations," noted prominent Swiss psychologist and philosopher Jean Piaget.

The goal of modern education is the individual's overall, balanced or harmonious growth. It includes moral, social, mental, intellectual, emotional, and physical development.

An adolescent's emotional behavior influences the individual's overall personality. Not only is it desirable, but it is important that boys and girls progressively acquire more and more control over their emotions during puberty and display emotional maturity in their everyday behavior.

The School Environment's Function in Education

"The learning environment is the most important component to assess the health of the school community if it is an ecosystem."

All external factors that impact a person's development, including those that come from both inside and outside the person, are included in the environment. The environment is defined by Douglas and Holland (1947) as the culmination of all outside factors, influences, and circumstances that have an impact on the existence, characteristics, behavior, and development of living things. Prenatal nutrition has an impact on development, and the environment continues to have an impact on people after delivery. It can be divided into physical, emotional, social, and mental aspects.

Adolescents' perceptions of the school environment are influenced by a number of variables, including the architectural layout, instructional strategies, and rate of change. Emotional and social maturity are supported in a healthy educational setting.

It consequently influences the conduct and academic performance of students.

Adolescence and Maturity

Significant physical, emotional, social, and intellectual changes occur during adolescence, a crucial time of transition in a person's life. Understanding that teenagers are not a monolithic group is crucial because their needs and difficulties differ based on sex, developmental stage, and socioeconomic background.

Emotional Maturity during Adolescence:

Emotions activate the powers of the imaginary and help cope with emergencies. Emotion is a person's extreme disturbance. It is the mental process that involves emotions and motor acts, an experience and activity that is driven by the internal structure of the individual.

During Adolescence, emotions change frequently and rapidly. It makes them moody. They are highly pleased at times and incredibly sad at other times, all of which occurs in a very short period of time. As a result, the nature of their emotional states is too ambiguous.

Emotionally mature adolescents have the capability to easily adapt to themselves, their families, school friends' community and society.

Emotional Maturity-Definition

A person will be called emotionally mature or emotionally intelligent when he or she can express proper emotions apt to the situations. Emotionally mature adolescents have the capability to easily adapt to themselves, their families, school friends' community and society.

A teenager spends much of his day in an educational institution where because of discipline and other environmental stresses, he has to face various kinds of circumstances when he is faced with the issue of emotional restraint. The researcher found it necessary to study the emotional behavior

of adolescent boys and girls studying in two different kinds of school environments, namely government and private school environment, and consequently emotional maturity.

It is crucial to investigate methodically how the educational environment affects teenagers' emotional maturity given the present research deficit. The purpose of this study is to provide insightful information that may guide curriculum adjustments in schools that include exercises and tactics intended to foster and improve kids' emotional development. In the end, it aims to enable students to develop into mature, responsible individuals. The results of this study will add to the growing corpus of research on the relationship between emotional maturity and the school environment.

The purpose of this study is to provide insightful information that may help update school curricula to include exercises and methods intended to foster and improve kids' emotional development. In the end, it aims to enable students to develop into mature, responsible individuals. The results of this study will add to the growing corpus of research on the relationship between emotional maturity and the school environment.

In this research, we shall be studying the, “Effect of School Environment on the Emotional Maturity of Adolescents Studying in Durg District”.

Key Terms:

Adolescence, school environment, emotional maturity, gender.

Operational Definitions:

1. Adolescence:

Students in the 11th standard who are between the ages of 16 and 18 regardless of caste, religion, or family status in public and private schools, were regarded as adolescents.

2. School Environment:

Operationally, the school environment is defined as the scores obtained by the subjects in School Environment Inventory standardized by K.S. Mishra. The definition given by Mishra (2000) about school environment has been used in the current study. Mishra states that the school environment refers to the general socio-psychological climate of school which provides conditions and opportunities to develop.

3. Emotional Maturity:

Operationally, **Emotional Maturity** is defined as the score obtained by the subject in Emotional Maturity Scale standardized by Tara Sabapathy.

4. Gender:

According to WHO (2023), gender refers to the characteristics of women, men, girls and boys that are socially constructed. This includes norms, behaviors and roles associated with being a woman, man, girl or boy, as well as relationships with others. In the current research, gender refers to male and female students taken for the study.

Objectives of the Study:

Purpose of this research was to investigate the effects of school environment, gender, and type of school, as well as the interactions between these factors, on emotional maturity of adolescents.

Hypotheses of the Study:

H₀I1-0 There will be no significant effect of school climate, gender, type of school and their interaction on emotional maturity of adolescents.

Significance of the Study:

Many changes occur among children during adolescence, which is the transition between childhood and adulthood, such as physical, mental, social, and moral in a rather abrupt manner. Adolescence, a developmental stage, marks the beginning of the more complex thinking processes or formal logical operations including abstract thinking, the ability to reason from known principles to form own new ideas or questions. Students who have a well emotional development are able to locate themselves in their surroundings, comprehend the prejudices they hold in the world, and are able to accept responsibility for how they present themselves in the world. With this in mind, the researcher saw a need to study “Effect of School Environment on the Emotional Maturity of Adolescents Studying in Durg District”.

Methodology of the study

Design of the Study: The present study was descriptive survey in nature. The research was carried out on adolescent students in Durg, Chhattisgarh.

Tools: i. School Environment inventory developed by Dr. K.S.Misra ii. Emotional Maturity Scale standardized by Tara Sabapathy.

Sample: Sample studying in Class XI was selected by Stratified Random Sampling technique and care was taken to select representative sample of boys/girls, government/private schools, adolescents from each block of Durg, Chhattisgarh and they had been attending that school for at least seven years. The present research work was conducted on 792 (20%) students of class XI were selected randomly from a total of 3960 students of 11th class from 44 randomly selected schools in Durg district, Chhattisgarh, India. Number of boys and girl students was kept equally in accordance with the blueprint for the study.

VARIABLES OF THE STUDY

Variables of a study are:

1. Dependent Variables

In present investigation, Emotional Maturity will be treated as dependent variables.

2. Independent Variable

School Environment will be considered as independent variables.

3. Demographic variables are:

(i) Type of school

(ii) Gender

Statistical Techniques: In order to analyse the data following statistical techniques were employed: i. Mean, Standard Deviation. ii. ANOVA (F- Value).

Result and Discussion

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

H₀11-0 There will be no significant effect of school climate, gender, type of school and their interaction on emotional maturity of adolescents.

Data obtained in response to this hypothesis was analyzed by employing $2 \times 2 \times 2$ FACTORIAL DESIGN ANOVA. Summary of this analysis has been arranged in table below:

Table -Summary of $2 \times 2 \times 2$ F D ANOVA for effect of school climate, gender, type of school and their interaction on emotional development

S.No.	Source of variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
1	School Climate	283.904	1	283.904	4.064*
2	Gender	33378.563	1	33378.563	477.794**
3	Type of School	18410.000	1	18410.000	263.528**
4	School Climate \times Gender	152.865	1	152.865	2.188NS
5	School Climate \times Type of School	.474	1	.474	.007NS
6	Gender \times Type of School	734.535	1	734.535	10.514**
7	School Climate \times Gender \times Type of School	17.172	1	17.172	.246NS
8	Error	54770.008	784	69.860	
9	Total	174847	792		
10	Corrected Total	121638.544	791		

** Significant at 0.01 level, *Significant at 0.05 level, NS Not Significant

EFFECT OF SCHOOL CLIMATE:

Table- Summary of mean and standard deviation of emotional development scores of favorable and unfavorable school climate.

School Climate	Mean	SD
Favorable School Climate	150.55	12.82
Unfavorable School Climate	145.71	11.54

EFFECT OF GENDER:

Table-Mean and standard deviation of emotional development scores of male and female adolescents.

Gender	Mean	SD
Male	140.74	10.03
Female	155.31	10.03

EFFECT OF TYPE OF SCHOOL:

Table-Mean and standard deviation of emotional development scores of government and private school adolescents

Type Of School	Mean	SD
Government	142.46	11.09
Private	153.59	11.07

EFFECT OF INTERACTION BETWEEN GENDER AND TYPE OF SCHOOL:

Graph: Interactional effect of sex and type of school on emotional development of adolescents.

From the graph, it is evident that emotional development of both male and female students studying in private school was higher than the students of government schools. This can also be concluded that in both government as well as private schools' emotional maturity of female students was higher than the male students.

Results:

- ❖ School climates produce a significant effect on emotional development of the students.
- ❖ Emotional development of the adolescents with favorable school climate was higher than the emotional development of the adolescents with unfavorable school climate.
- ❖ Gender produces a significant effect on emotional development of the students.
- ❖ Emotional development of the Female adolescents was higher than the emotional development of the male adolescents.
- ❖ Type of school produce a significant effect on emotional development of the students.
- ❖ Emotional development of the adolescents studying in private school was higher than the emotional development of the adolescents studying in government school.
- ❖ Interaction between school climate and gender do not produce a significant effect on emotional development of the students.
- ❖ Interaction between school climate and type of school do not produce a significant effect on emotional development of the students.
- ❖ Interaction between gender and type of school produces a significant effect on emotional development of the students.
- ❖ Emotional development of both male and female students studying in private school was higher than the students of government schools. This can also be concluded that in both government as well as private schools' emotional maturity of female students was higher than the male students.
- ❖ Interaction between school climate, gender and type of school did not produce any significant effect on emotional development of the students.

Findings and Discussion:

- The findings of the present study indicate that Gender produce a significant effect on emotional maturity of the students and Emotional maturity of the male adolescents was higher than the emotional maturity of the female adolescents. In agreement with the

findings of the current investigation, the researchers **Arya. A, (1984), Singh, R.P. (1993), Geeta S. Pastey and Vijayalaxmi A. Aminbhavi, (2006), Subbarayan, G. Visvanathan, (2011) , Lakshmi, S. and Krishnamurthy, S (2011)Kumar, Tiwari Vinit (2012) , (Subramanian, 2013), Sunil Kumar (2014), Malliick Rinku, Singh Archana, Chaturvedi Poonam & Kumar Narendra (2014), Brahmhat S (2016), Kaur,S.(2017), Vyas T, & Gunthey R (2017), Dave Anjali (2019), Mitalben M. Jadav& Dr. N.M. Tajpuria(2019), Ghosh, S. (2019)**also reported that boys had better emotional maturity than girls.

High emotional maturity in boys may be because boys are more extroverted, expressive, have progressive outlook, tough, and have more toleration as compared to girls who by nature are shy, introverted, sensitive and less expressive. The male adolescents had more emotional maturity than female early adolescents. This may be because male adolescents understood emotions and expressed them at appropriate times.

This difference in emotional maturity may be because emotional response to moral conflict which is exemplified by males more than females results in better adult male reasoning. Female decisions are probably less empathic and more impartial and detached, whereas male decisions are probably influenced by empathy and emotion.

- The findings of the present study indicate that School climate produce a significant effect on emotional maturity of the students and Emotional maturity of the adolescents studying in private school was higher than the emotional maturity of the adolescents studying in government school. Consistent with the present study findings the researchers **Gakhar, S. C. (2005) Subramanian and Veliappan (2013) Deva Anjali (2015). Nath (2015), Nikhat Yasmin Shafeeq & Afeefa Thaqib (2015), Rajni Mahendra & Ravindra Kumar Thakur (2018), Das, Juri & Padmavathy, R.D. (2019), Babita, Ishrat Naaz (2021),** also reported that the type of school played an important role, where private school students had better emotional maturity than government school students. **Singh, R., Pant, K. and Valentina, L. (2017)** also reported that boys were found to score higher on the emotional maturity component of social adjustment.

Private school pupils are more emotionally mature than the student of government school. It's possible that this is because children attending private schools receive superior care to that of those attending public schools. Adolescents of private recognized schools generally come from affluent families, get more individual attention more teaching learning facilities, better attention by their parents as compared to adolescents of government schools. The reason for better emotional maturity level of adolescents of private schools may be that in such schools' students get more planned curriculum, along with the cognitive and conative domain, their affective domain of personality is also taken care of. There are provisions of various co-curricular activities for the adolescents which help them give expression to their feelings and make them balanced human beings. Thirdly in private schools there is more interaction between the teachers and students and thus students get counselling for the personal, social, emotional, and vocational problems. Government school students of the state are generally ill

equipped for all these things and thus lag behind in emotional maturity in comparison to their counterparts. Furthermore, students at private schools have had more encounters and contact with the society, leading to a greater number of bitter and pleasurable experiences, both of which contribute to their development into emotionally mature adults. Considering things from this angle, government educational institution must provide some sort of coverage to be exposed to society or to gain first-hand experience in a variety of settings while they are still in school. This will help them become emotionally mature people who are capable of living their lives freely.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATION

The findings of the study “Effect of School Environment on the Emotional Maturity of Adolescents studying in Durg District, C.G.” have important educational implications. A positive and supportive school environment can significantly enhance adolescents’ emotional maturity by promoting emotional stability, self-control, empathy, and healthy social relationships. Schools should therefore focus on creating a safe, inclusive, and stress-free climate through effective teacher–student interaction, peer cooperation, and participative learning practices. Teachers need training in emotional sensitivity and classroom management to identify and address students’ emotional needs. Guidance and counseling services should be strengthened to support adolescents facing emotional challenges. Incorporating life-skills education, value education, and co-curricular activities can further foster emotional maturity, leading to better academic performance and overall personality development.

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